

Improvement Project under heavy field incidence during 1986 kharif and 1987 rabi. Each accession was planted in 10-m² plots with a spacing of 20 × 15 cm, with two replications. Accessions were scored at panicle initiation (PI), when infestation was more than 200 insects/hill.

Eight accessions were found to be highly resistant (score 1) (see table). One was resistant (score 2) and six were moderately resistant (score 3-5). Twelve entries were moderately susceptible (score 5-7) and 15 were highly susceptible (score 7-9).

Almost all the highly resistant entries were derived from crosses involving ARC6650 or Velluthacheera. Resistant entry KAU153-1 was derived from IR1561/PTB33. □

Reaction of differential rice varieties to Manipur biotype of gall midge (GM)

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Seven GM *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason biotypes have been identified, one each in China, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and Thailand, and three in India (Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, and Ranchi [Bihar]).

We evaluated six differentials (four donors and two derivatives from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad) against the GM population of Iroisemba, Manipur, in 1988 wet season. Thirty-day-old seedlings were planted in 3-m rows per variety at 15-

× 15-cm spacing. GM incidence was recorded at 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT).

Potential donors Eswarakora and Banglei showed low damage; Leuang 152 and Velluthacheera showed higher. Resistant derivative W1263 showed no

damage; Phalguna was susceptible to the local GM population (see table).

These reactions of proven donors and derivatives show that the Manipur GM biotype conforms to the Ranchi GM biotype. □

Reaction of donors and derivatives to GM. Iroisemba, Manipur, India, 1988.

Variety	Donor, derivative	GM incidence (%)			
		30 DT		50 DT	
		Infested hills	Silvershoots	Infested hills	Silvershoots
Eswarakora	Donor	5	1	5	1
W1263	MTU15/Eswarakora	0	0	0	0
Phalguna	IR8/Siam 29	25	10	75	23
Leuang 152	Donor	15	4	35	10
Velluthacheera	Donor	0	0	50	12
Banglei	Donor	0	0	0	0
TN1	Susceptible check	30	11	75	29

Resistance of wild rices to insect pests

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We evaluated 185 wild rice accessions--16 species, 4 natural hybrids, and an unknown *Oryza* sp.—against *Nilaparvata lugens*, *Nephotettix virescens*, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, *Marasmia patnalis*, *Rivula atimeta*, *Hydrellia philippina*, and *Nymphula depunctalis*.

Reactions to planthoppers and leafhoppers were tested using the standard seedbox screening test. Reactions against foliage feeders were tested in the greenhouse. Resistance to *S. incertulas* and *N. depunctalis* was

Table 1. Resistance of wild rices to selected species of insect pests. IIRI, 1988.

Insect	Accessions tested (no.)	Resistant	
		no.	%
<i>N. lugens</i> biotype 1	185	87	47
<i>N. lugens</i> biotype 2	185	66	36
<i>N. lugens</i> biotype 3	185	78	42
<i>N. virescens</i>	184	68	37
<i>S. furcifera</i>	185	83	45
<i>S. incertulas</i>	177	41	23
<i>C. medinalis</i>	176	0	0
<i>M. patnalis</i>	176	0	0
<i>R. atimeta</i>	176	0	0
<i>H. philippina</i>	172	13	8
<i>N. depunctalis</i>	172	0	0

evaluated in plants grown in concrete beds. Resistance to *H. philippina* was tested under natural infestation in the field. Plant damage was rated on a 0-9 scale.

Nearly 50% of the accessions were

Table 2. Species of wild rices with multiple resistance to *N. lugens*, *S. furcifera*, *N. virescens*, *S. incertulas*, and *H. philippina*. IIRI, 1988.

Species	IIRI Acc. no.	Origin
<i>O. alta</i>	100111	Surinam
<i>O. australiensis</i>	105165	Australia
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	105159	Uganda
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	105163	Uganda
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	105144	Brazil
<i>O. latifolia</i>	105142	Costa Rica
<i>O. minuta</i>	105126	Philippines
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100176	Unknown
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105079	India
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105088	Malaysia
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105119	Philippines
<i>O. punctata</i>	100886	Unknown
<i>O. punctata</i>	105158	Uganda

resistant to *S. furcifera* and *N. lugens* biotypes 1 and 3, more than 35% to biotype 2 and *N. virescens*, 23% to *S. incertulas*, and 8% to *H. philippina* (Table 1). No accession was resistant